

Conceptual Design and Technology Sensitivity Analysis of a Fuel Cell Short- Range Aircraft

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This work presents conceptual design activities carried out within the Clean Aviation FAME (Fuel cell propulsion system for Aircraft Megawatt Engines) project, focused on a liquid hydrogen and fuel-cell-powered short-range aircraft targeting a 2035 entry into service. A parametric analysis framework was developed to support the definition and optimization of aircraft-level architectures under realistic regulatory and technological constraints. Trade studies were conducted to investigate the influence of LH₂ tank design parameters and propulsion system layout on fuel consumption and overall performance. The current FAME concept aircraft—featuring four 2.5 MW fuel cell propulsion systems and a 110 m² wing—is introduced and assessed. A final sensitivity analysis evaluates the configuration’s robustness to degraded fuel cell efficiency and increased drag due to thermal management integration. Results demonstrate that performance deteriorates nonlinearly as technological assumptions degrade, reinforcing the need to maintain high fuel cell efficiency and effective integration of cooling systems to ensure compliance with mission and regulatory requirements.

I. Nomenclature

<i>ASL</i>	= air supply line	<i>MAC</i>	= mean aerodynamic chord
<i>C_{D,0}</i>	= zero-lift drag coefficient	<i>MDO</i>	= multidisciplinary design optimization
<i>CAS</i>	= calibrated air speed	<i>MLM</i>	= maximum landing mass
<i>CG</i>	= center of gravity	<i>MTOM</i>	= maximum take-off mass
<i>CGR</i>	= climb gradient	<i>OEI</i>	= one engine inoperative
<i>CL</i>	= cooling line	<i>OEM</i>	= operating empty mass
<i>EIS</i>	= entry into service	<i>PEMFC</i>	= proton exchange membrane fuel cell
<i>eVTOL</i>	= electric vertical take-off and landing	<i>PL</i>	= power line
<i>FL</i>	= flight level	<i>RH</i>	= right hand
<i>ICAC</i>	= initial cruise altitude capability	<i>SL</i>	= sea level
<i>ISA</i>	= International Standard Atmosphere	<i>SOFC</i>	= solid oxide fuel cell
<i>FCS</i>	= fuel cell system	<i>TLAR</i>	= top-level aircraft requirement
<i>LH</i>	= left hand	<i>TMS</i>	= thermal management system
<i>LH₂</i>	= liquid hydrogen	<i>TOFL</i>	= take-off field length

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II. Introduction

The aviation industry is a cornerstone of modern global transportation, enabling economic growth and cultural exchange. However, it also contributes significantly to environmental challenges, accounting for approximately 2–3% of global CO₂ emissions [1]. With the increasing demand for air travel, particularly in the regional/short-range aviation market, mitigating the environmental impact of aviation has become a critical priority. Achieving net-zero emissions by mid-century, a target advocated by international organizations such as ICAO and IATA [2][3], requires the development of innovative aircraft technologies and energy systems.

While incremental improvements in airframe design, aerodynamics, and conventional thermal engines can enhance fuel efficiency and reduce emissions, these measures alone are insufficient to meet stringent environmental targets. The transition to zero-emission aircraft necessitates the adoption of disruptive technologies, such as electric propulsion systems powered by alternative energy sources like hydrogen. Among these, liquid hydrogen combined with fuel cells represents a particularly promising solution due to its high energy density, potential for zero operational emissions—except water and the potential for contrail formation—and compatibility with renewable energy production pathways.

However, integrating these technologies into viable aircraft designs poses significant challenges. The unique characteristics of hydrogen storage, fuel cell systems, and associated subsystems demand substantial modifications to traditional aircraft architectures, often necessitating departures from or significant adaptations to conventional tube-and-wing configurations. These changes impact overall aircraft performance, requiring comprehensive analyses to evaluate their feasibility and identify optimal design solutions. Accurately modeling the performance, mass, and space allocation of such novel propulsion systems is crucial for understanding their effect on flight performance, but it is equally important to maintain computational efficiency, enabling broad design explorations within reasonable timeframes. A careful selection of the most impactful parameters, coupled with the construction and adoption of surrogate models derived from high-fidelity analyses, is essential to achieve fast, reliable design evaluations.

Recent years have seen a substantial growth in literature examining the feasibility and design integration of fuel-cell-powered aircraft, particularly in the context of liquid hydrogen (LH₂) as the primary energy vector.

A significant portion of this research has focused on system-level conceptual design and propulsion architecture integration. Kiely and Agarwal [4] conducted a comprehensive analysis of hydrogen fuel cell propulsion for short- to mid-range commercial aircraft, including hybrid configurations where batteries supplement the fuel cells during peak power demand. They developed an automated toolchain to analyze multiple configurations and concluded that fuel cell systems could become technologically viable and efficient by 2035. Similarly, Waddington et al. [5] investigated a single-aisle aircraft concept using LH₂ and fuel cells, demonstrating that distributed electric propulsion, coupled with thermal and air management, could yield performance comparable to modern aircraft by 2050. Their work also included an assessment of performance degradation due to fuel cell aging. A broader comparative study by Karpuk et al. [6] assessed the potential of fuel cell aircraft versus hydrogen combustion counterparts for medium- and long-range commercial applications, concluding that although fuel cell aircraft have higher operating costs and fuel burn, they offer significant climate benefits, particularly for long-range missions. Likewise, Pustina et al. [7] presented a multidisciplinary optimization framework tailored to new propulsion technologies, demonstrating the benefits of hydrogen and hybrid-electric systems in regional aviation when a high-fidelity, weight-sensitive optimization scheme is used. Further, Proesmans and Vos [8] incorporated climate impact objectives into the conceptual design of LH₂ aircraft using gas turbine engines, concluding that contrail avoidance altitudes significantly reduce global warming potential, albeit at the cost of higher energy use and operating costs.

Complementary to these aircraft-level investigations are studies focusing on system retrofitting and incremental integration. Rischmueller et al. [9] explored the retrofit of the D328eco regional aircraft with a parallel hybrid dual-fuel system combining high-temperature fuel cells and turboshafts. Their work emphasized hybridization strategies and payload trade-offs, supported by off-design mission analysis and environmental impact assessments. Habrard et al. [10] conducted a sensitivity study on a retrofitted hybrid fuel cell aircraft, examining interactions between the thermal management system (TMS), fuel cell operating conditions, and aircraft-level performance. Their findings highlighted how cruise speed, ambient conditions, and TMS configuration influence emissions and payload capacity.

Several studies have delved into the critical role of thermal management. Sain et al. [11] performed a detailed conceptual design of air and thermal management components within nacelle-integrated low-temperature proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) systems. They compared axial and annular layouts for heat exchangers and demonstrated how geometry and placement affect integration, drag, and cooling performance. Guo et al. [12] examined two cooling strategies—ducted radiators and outer mold line heat exchangers—and quantified the resulting thermal fluxes and drag penalties. Both studies underscore the importance of dedicated air cooling designs early in the aircraft design process.

Hydrogen tank sizing and integration has also received close attention. Burschik et al. [13] studied the trade-offs between tank insulation (rigid foam vs. multilayer), venting strategies, and aerodynamic penalties, demonstrating how tank placement and thermal efficiency influence block fuel and dormancy time. Onorato et al. [14] expanded this line of work by comparing various tank configurations across different aircraft classes. They showed that tank integration strategies, such as using forward tanks or optimizing venting pressure, depend strongly on mission requirements and aircraft category.

Exploratory design studies on novel configurations complete the current landscape. Chung et al. [15] investigated hydrogen solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) coupled with gas turbine engine propulsion for both blended-wing-body and conventional layouts, finding strong emissions reductions but substantial differences in take-off weight and system complexity. Keijzer et al. [16] demonstrated the application of multidisciplinary design optimization (MDO) techniques to design a hydrogen-powered electric vertical take-off and landing (eVTOL), revealing design penalties tied to hydrogen storage but also improved long-range performance potential. Recently, Palaia et al. [17] explored a non-conventional box-wing configuration retrofitted for LH₂ propulsion. Their study, focused on medium-range missions, compared tank integration strategies and revealed that box-wing designs can enable extended range or high payload, but not both simultaneously, due to volumetric limitations introduced by LH₂ storage.

Together, these studies provide a robust foundation for ongoing efforts to assess and optimize LH₂-powered short-range aircraft. This research is conducted within the framework of the Clean Aviation FAME project^{††} (Fuel cell propulsion system for Aircraft Megawatt Engines), coordinated by Airbus, which aims to pave the way for a compact, lightweight, and high-efficiency electric propulsion system tailored to short-range aircraft. The envisioned powertrain is based on an aviation-native fuel cell system powered by liquid hydrogen and delivering multi-megawatt power levels in the range of 2–4 MW, integrated with all sub- and auxiliary systems, including nacelles and propellers. In particular, the activities presented in this paper contribute to Work Package 2 (WP2), which focuses on aircraft-level conceptual design and propulsion system integration. The WP2 objectives include an MDO of a full-scale electric drivetrain embedded into a short-range aircraft platform (101 passengers, 1,000 nm range, FL270 cruise flight), with each configuration featuring either four or six 2.5 MW-class fuel cell propulsion units.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section III presents the tools and methodologies employed throughout the study, including the conceptual aircraft design framework and the surrogate model developed to estimate LH₂ tank characteristics. Section IV defines the design constraints through a comprehensive overview of the top-level aircraft requirements and the technological assumptions adopted for the propulsion system. The main results are discussed in Section V. This includes an optimization of the LH₂ tank venting pressure, an evaluation of the most suitable engine configuration, a detailed description of the current FAME concept aircraft, and a two-part sensitivity analysis investigating the impact of fuel cell efficiency and cooling drag assumptions on design robustness. Finally, Section VI provides the concluding remarks and outlines future research directions within the FAME project.

III. Tools and methodologies

A. JPAD aircraft design library

JPAD is the tool used for aircraft-related studies in this work [18][19][20]. It is a comprehensive suite of tools and libraries for aircraft conceptual and preliminary design, developed by the DAF research group at the University of Naples Federico II and SmartUp Engineering, a spin-off company of the same university. Primarily written in Java with an object-oriented approach, the JPAD library offers a detailed aircraft parameterization suitable for preliminary design tasks, supported by an intuitive user interface. On the analysis side, JPAD facilitates multidisciplinary analyses for conventional tube-and-wing configurations, including mass breakdowns, center of gravity estimations, aerodynamic assessments, and performance evaluations. The typical analysis workflow for a newly designed aircraft, as enabled by JPAD, is shown in Fig. 1. To estimate structural and onboard systems masses, center of gravity positions, and aerodynamic coefficients, JPAD implements well-established semi-empirical equations from the literature [21][22][23][24][25][26] or in-house developed methods [27][28][29]. Performance analyses are conducted using a simulation-based approach, solving systems of ordinary differential equations when necessary [18][20].

The current powerplant parameterization implemented in JPAD enables the analysis of unconventional configurations incorporating emerging propulsion technologies, such as batteries and fuel cells. The input for the powerplant is provided through an XML file that contains information on power sources (fuel tank systems, batteries, and fuel cells) and actual power units. These units may consist of one or more thermal engines or electric motors

^{††} <https://clean-aviation.eu/fame>

operating in parallel, along with a reduction gearbox (if required), and a propeller or fan. The behavior of batteries and fuel cells is modeled using a bottom-up approach, starting at the cell level. Users have the option to customize this behavior, or they can rely on default built-in cycling and polarization curves. The complete system characteristics, including net output power, efficiency, total mass, and total volume, are derived based on instructions for system design, such as power sizing and voltage sizing. Subsystems and auxiliary components, including power off-takes and efficiency losses, are considered when estimating the total system efficiency and available power, as well as their contribution to the overall mass of the powerplant. Feeding tanks can be of three types—integral, rigid, and bladder—and must be characterized in terms of position, size, shape, wall thickness, fuel characteristics, and mass.

Fig. 1 JPAD-implemented design and analysis workflow

B. LH₂ tank characteristics surrogate model

For this study, a surrogate model is developed to characterize the LH₂ storage system. The surrogate model is built using a MATLAB code that implements the approach described by Winnefeld et al. [30], based on approximately 1,000 simulations. These simulations involve key design parameters such as the tank's internal diameter, venting pressure, LH₂ mass to be stored, and the mission profile. The mission profile includes an initial ground phase lasting 240 minutes under ISA+40°C conditions, during which the LH₂ tank must maintain integrity without requiring venting. For other design parameters, constant values are selected and kept fixed during the simulations: the insulation type is defined as vacuum plus multi-layer insulation (Dacron, double aluminized polyester film), the trapped fuel mass is set to 10% of the total LH₂ mass to be stored, the vessel cap geometry is fixed as elliptic with a radius equal to a quarter of the tank's internal diameter, and the material for structures and stiffening is chosen as Aluminum 2219. The surrogate model outputs the tank's characteristics, including mass, insulation thickness, and overall length. The decision to build a surrogate model, rather than directly using the MATLAB code to estimate the LH₂ tank characteristics, is driven by computational considerations. Since the time required to converge on a final LH₂ tank design is comparable to the time needed to run the aircraft analyses, a reduced-order model is preferred to optimize the design process for the LH₂ tank.

C. FAME conceptual design framework

The design and analysis process implemented using the JPAD library for the FAME project is illustrated in Fig. 2. This parametric framework enables systematic exploration of LH₂-fueled aircraft configurations under consistent performance and integration constraints, incorporating multidisciplinary analyses and iterative convergence loops.

The process begins with the initialization of a baseline aircraft configuration, generated through statistical pre-design and enriched by technology-level assumptions. These include gravimetric and volumetric power densities for key powerplant subsystems, fuel cell efficiency curves, and airframe-related parameters such as structural technology level and onboard systems architecture. The input data are processed within the aircraft update block, which revises the geometry according to a structured set of variables. These include:

- Design variables, such as wing planform area, number of engines, and fuel cell sizing power per engine;
- Fixed variables, including wing span, cabin layout, fuselage cross section, and tail volumetric and aspect ratios;
- Derived variables, such as wing aspect ratio, fuselage central trunk length, nacelle dimensions, tailplane geometry and position, and main landing gear location.

A key component of this update process is the LH₂ tank surrogate model, which predicts tank mass, insulation and structural thickness, and geometric dimensions as a function of hydrogen mass and venting pressure.

The updated aircraft is then passed to the analysis framework, which features two main iterative convergence loops. The first is the mission fuel loop of Fig. 1. Once convergence on block fuel and maximum take-off mass (MTOM) is reached, the LH₂ tank sizing loop evaluates whether the installed tank volume is compatible with the required hydrogen mass. If not, the tank geometry—and by extension, the fuselage—is adaptively updated until convergence is achieved.

Once both loops have converged, a complete performance analysis is conducted. This includes detailed simulations of take-off, climb, cruise, descent, and landing, as well as optional analyses of alternative mission profiles and payload-range characteristics. Outputs are consolidated into a comprehensive aircraft analysis report. Additionally, response surfaces are generated to enable post-processing, trend identification, and support for optimization tasks.

Fig. 2 FAME-specific conceptual aircraft design framework built with the JPAD library.

IV. Requirements

A. Top-level aircraft requirements

Table 1 summarizes the TLARs established for the design of a fully electric, fuel cell-powered short-range aircraft. These specifications, defined by Airbus, were selected to represent a feasible yet ambitious performance envelope aligned with a prospective market niche for LH₂-powered zero-emission aircraft. The targeted entry into service (EIS) in 2035 sets the technological horizon, particularly in terms of propulsion and energy storage systems.

The design mission specifies a range of 1,000 nautical miles and a seating capacity of 101 passengers, assuming an average weight of 95 kg per passenger. These values exceed those of current-generation regional/short-range turboprops, indicating an intention to address higher-capacity and longer-range segments. A cruise Mach number of 0.55 further underlines the emphasis on improving cruise performance and market competitiveness.

Operational and regulatory constraints are also embedded in the TLARs. These include a take-off field length (TOFL) of no more than 1,400 meters at sea level, under ISA+15°C conditions at MTOM, and a landing field length (LFL) requirement of less than 1,400 meters at maximum landing mass (MLM) under the same atmospheric conditions. The aircraft must fall within Design Group III (wing span between 24 and 36 meters) and comply with Approach Category C standards, requiring an approach calibrated air speed (CAS) between 121 and 140 knots.

High-altitude airport operability is supported by a take-off altitude capability of up to 14,600 feet and a one-engine-inoperative (OEI) ceiling requirement above 10,000 feet. Additionally, the aircraft must demonstrate an initial cruise altitude capability (ICAC) of 27,000 feet with a minimum rate of climb of 300 feet per minute at this altitude. While not formally specified by Airbus, an additional constraint—limiting the time to reach FL270 to less than 25 minutes—was introduced in the current study to further ensure realistic mission performance.

Finally, the mission profile must accommodate standard commercial reserves, including 100 nm of diversion, 30 minutes of holding, and 5% contingency fuel. Together, these requirements form the design envelope used to assess the feasibility and performance of alternative configurations investigated in this work.

Table 1 Set of top-level aircraft requirements selected for the conceptual design of the FAME aircraft.

Requirement	Value
EIS	2035
Design range	1,000 nm
Number of passengers	101 @95 kg
Cruise Mach number	0.55
ICAC	27,000 ft
Rate of climb at ICAC	300 ft/min
OEI ceiling	> 10,000 ft
TOFL @MTOM, SL, ISA+15°C	1,400 m
Take-off altitude	Up to 14,600 ft
Aircraft approach category	Category C (121 ≤ Approach CAS ≤ 140 kn)
LFL @MLM, SL, ISA+15°C	< 1,400 m
Aircraft design group	Group III (24 < wing span < 36 m)
Reserve	100 nm diversion, 30 min holding, 5% trip fuel

B. Powerplant requirements

The powerplant configuration adopted for the analyses is illustrated in Fig. 3. The system is centered around an LH₂ storage tank that supplies hydrogen to multiple fuel cell systems (FCS) housed within wing-mounted nacelles. Each FCS consists of multiple fuel cell stacks operating in parallel, ensuring scalability and redundancy. Oxygen required for the fuel cell reaction, as well as cooling capability, is provided by two dedicated subsystems: an air supply line (ASL) and a cooling line (CL). The ASL includes an air compressor designed to overcome pressure losses at high altitudes, while the CL incorporates one or more heat exchangers to maintain optimal operating temperatures. Each FCS is equipped with its own set of ancillary systems to support its operation. The electrical power generated by the fuel cells is transferred to the propeller via an electric motor and a reduction gearbox, collectively referred to as the power line (PL).

The key assumptions regarding powerplant technology levels are summarized in Table 2. Dealing with the LH₂ tanks, the assumptions described in Subsection III.B apply. For the FCS, gravimetric and volumetric power densities of 2.0 kW/kg and 2.0 kW/l, respectively, are assumed. These values are used to estimate the FCS mass and volume based on its sizing power. The FCS efficiency is set at 55% for maximum power and increases at partial load, reaching

up to 65% at minimum power (set as 10% of peak power). For the ASL, a gravimetric power density of 7.1 kW/kg is assumed. This value is used to calculate the ASL mass by dividing the FCS design power by it. Similarly, a gravimetric power density of 3.0 kW/kg is assumed for the CL, allowing for the estimation of the heat exchangers' mass based on the FCS design power and efficiency. These subsystems collectively result in altitude-dependent power losses, which are modeled with a linear behavior: approximately 8.0% of the FCS power at SL and increasing to about 20.0% at 27,000 ft. For altitudes higher than 27,000 ft, this linear behavior is extrapolated. Regarding the PL, the electric motor, including the inverter and cables contributions, is assumed to have a gravimetric power density of 5.0 kW/kg. The total efficiency of the PL is set at a constant value of 94%. It is assumed that the onboard systems require a constant non-propulsive power supply of 200 kW, equally shared between the installed engines.

Fig. 3 Exemplification of the propulsion scheme adopted for the FAME aircraft.

Table 2 Powerplant performance requirements.

Powerplant-related variable	Value
<i>Hydrogen tank</i>	
Hydrogen gravimetric energy density	33.3 kWh/kg
Tank technology	Cryogenic
Capability	240 min @ISA+40°C w/o venting
Insulation	Vacuum + multi-layer insulation
Number of tanks	2
<i>Fuel cell system (FCS)</i>	
Gravimetric power density	2.0 kW/kg
Volumetric power density	2.0 kW/l
Efficiency @max. power	55.0%
Efficiency @min. power	65.0%
Nominal voltage	850 V
<i>FCS air supply line (ASL) and cooling line (CL)</i>	
ASL gravimetric power density	7.1 kW/kg
CL gravimetric power density	3.0 kW/kg
FCS-generated heat % removed through the exhaust	10.0%
ASL+CL FCS power extraction @SL, ISA	8.0%
ASL+CL FCS power extraction @8500 m, ISA	19.0%
<i>Power line (PL)</i>	
Electric motor + inverter gravimetric + cables power density	5.0 kW/kg
Electric motor efficiency	96.0%
Inverter efficiency	99.0%

Cables efficiency		99.5%
Reduction gearbox efficiency		99.4%
	<i>Non-propulsive demand</i>	
<u>Non-propulsive power demand</u>		<u>200 kW</u>

C. Baseline aircraft

Using the statistical pre-design tool integrated within the JPAD user interface, and based on the TLARs of Table 1 and the powerplant assumptions in Table 2, three baseline aircraft configurations were generated. Each corresponds to one of the engine layouts considered in this study: 2, 4, and 6 engines. The pre-design tool accepts TLARs as input and derives plausible configurations by leveraging statistical correlations obtained from existing aircraft with comparable performance and mission requirements.

Following their initial generation, all three configurations were manually updated to incorporate a preliminary LH₂ tank system, positioned in the aft section of the fuselage, after the rear bulkhead. The baseline aircraft share a common general layout: high-wing architecture, T-tail empennage, and podded, wing-mounted propeller-driven engines. The main landing gear is housed within a fairing located beneath the fuselage. The fuselage and cabin remain identical across the three configurations. These shared characteristics are summarized in Table 3 and are maintained throughout the parametric study, irrespective of variations in LH₂ tank size or geometry

In consideration of the targeted 2035 EIS, technological calibration factors have been applied to the semi-empirical models embedded in JPAD, already tailored to regional/short-range-class, propeller-driven aircraft. Specifically, correction factors ranging from 85% to 90% were introduced in the estimation of structural and interior masses to account for anticipated advancements in materials and lightweight systems. Similarly, a 25% reduction has been applied to the estimation of excrescence and interference drag coefficients, reflecting the integration of smoother aerodynamic surfaces and more advanced external configurations than those typical of current-generation regional/short-range aircraft. Unless otherwise specified, the results presented do not account for the aerodynamic drag contribution of the fuel cell cooling system. Among the analyses discussed in Section V, a dedicated sensitivity study investigates the impact of varying levels of cooling drag recovery on overall aircraft performance.

Table 3 Characteristics of the fuselage and cabin common to all the statistically defined baseline aircraft.

Parameter	Value
<i>Fuselage</i>	
Overall length	38.0 m
Central trunk maximum width	3.50 m
Central trunk maximum height	3.50 m
<i>Cabin</i>	
Seats	101
Abreast	2+3
Pitch	30 in
Cabin width	3.20 m
Cabin length	20.0 m
Cabin crew	3
Passenger door (LH, fwd)	0.86 × 1.83 m (type B)
Passenger door (LH, aft)	0.76 × 1.65 m (type C)
Service doors (RH, fwd; RH, aft)	0.76 × 1.65 m (type C)
Lavatories	2 (fwd & aft)
Wardrobes	1 (fwd)
Galleys	1 (aft)

V. Results

A. LH₂ tank optimization

This first study focuses on the optimization of LH₂ tank design parameters, with particular emphasis on identifying the most favorable venting pressure setting. The analysis is conducted using the surrogate model introduced in Subsection III.B, and is applied to the four-engine reference aircraft described in Subsection IV.C. Four different maximum venting pressure values are investigated: 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 bar.

For each pressure level, a dedicated parametric optimization was performed by varying the wing planform area and the individual FCS sizing power, with the objective of minimizing the block fuel required to complete the 1,000 nm design mission while satisfying the TLARs summarized in Table 1. The outcomes of these studies are synthesized in Fig. 4, while the key configuration parameters and performance metrics corresponding to the optimal design point for each pressure setting are detailed in Table 4.

Fig. 4 Effect of LH₂ tank venting pressure on aircraft characteristics and performance.

Table 4 Characteristics of optimal aircraft resulting from the LH₂ tank venting pressure study.

	LH ₂ tank venting pressure, bar			
	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
<i>Optimal aircraft design parameters</i>				
Wing planform area, m ²	109.24	100.0	100.0	100.0
Single FCS sizing power, kW	2,563	2,355	2,395	2,483
<i>Optimal aircraft characteristics</i>				
Sizing H ₂ mass, kg	1,722.8	1,564.1	1,571.7	1,589.9
Total installed power, kW	10,252	9,419	9,581	9,933
Overall fuselage length, m	39.58	37.23	37.16	37.22
MTOM, kg	48,839	44,864	45,234	46,074
Block fuel 1,000 nm mission, kg	1,301.0	1,181.6	1,186.9	1,199.8
Block fuel 250 nm mission, kg	361.8	328.1	330.1	335.0

Fig. 4 illustrates how tank venting pressure influences several critical parameters. As venting pressure increases, the total tank thickness—including structural walls and insulation—decreases significantly, especially between 1.5 and 2.0 bar. This reduction enables shorter tanks and, consequently, a more compact rear fuselage. However, while insulation mass benefits from higher pressures, structural requirements for tank walls and stiffeners become more demanding, leading to increased structural mass. These competing effects are reflected in the evolution of the

gravimetric index, which improves markedly from 1.5 to 2.0 bar, but then begins to deteriorate as structural mass outweighs further insulation savings.

The resulting impact on aircraft-level performance is non-negligible. From 1.5 to 2.0 bar, the aircraft sees a significant drop in MTOM, primarily driven by the improved gravimetric efficiency of the tank, the reduction in tank and fuselage length, and the corresponding reductions in powerplant mass and wing area required to meet performance constraints. Beyond 2.0 bar, these benefits diminish as the declining gravimetric index leads to an increase in the sizing hydrogen mass, setting off a cascade effect: greater fuel mass requires larger tanks, which in turn increases MTOM, requiring increased total installed power to maintain performance compliance.

Table 4 provides additional insight into the optimization results, detailing the values of the key design variables (wing area and FCS sizing power) and resulting aircraft characteristics for each venting pressure. These results confirm that, although fuselage length continues to decrease slightly beyond 2.0 bar (due to the continuing reduction in tank thickness), the snowball effect associated with declining tank gravimetric efficiency leads to an overall increase in block fuel, MTOM, and installed power. Notably, the configuration corresponding to a venting pressure of 2.0 bar yields the most favorable results across multiple performance metrics: the lowest MTOM (44,864 kg), lowest total installed power (9,419 kW), lowest block fuel consumption (1,181.6 kg for the design mission, 328.1 kg for a typical, 250 nm mission), and a compact fuselage (37.23 m). These results clearly highlight 2.0 bar as the optimal compromise between thermal insulation efficiency and structural mass penalties, providing a highly integrated tank design that minimizes both hydrogen usage and propulsion system demands, while enabling a more compact and lighter aircraft configuration.

B. Optimal number of engines

This second study investigates the influence of the number of engines on overall aircraft performance, with the goal of identifying the optimal engine configuration for the LH₂-powered short-range aircraft concept. Building on the results of Subsection V.A, all analyses here are conducted under the assumption of a fixed LH₂ tank venting pressure of 2.0 bar, previously identified as the optimal value.

Three configurations are considered: aircraft equipped with 2, 4, or 6 wing-mounted engines, each powered by an independent FCS. As in previous analyses, for each engine count, a parametric study and an optimization were performed, varying the wing planform area and the sizing power of the individual FCS to minimize block fuel consumption over a 1,000 nm design mission. These studies were carried out under the TLARs outlined in Table 1.

Fig. 5 through Fig. 7 present the block fuel contour maps for the 2-, 4-, and 6-engine configurations, respectively, along with the active constraints that define the feasible design regions. In each case, the optimal solution is indicated, and the impact of TLARs on narrowing the feasible design envelope is clearly visible.

In the 2-engine configuration (Fig. 5), the design is strongly constrained by OEI take-off performance and minimum approach speed, which drive the configuration toward higher individual FCS power (above 5.2 MW) and a wing planform area of nearly 110 m². These requirements lead to a propulsion system and structural mass increase, resulting in the highest MTOM among all configurations (46,565 kg). While this solution benefits from reduced parasitic drag due to fewer nacelles and their associated wing interference, the larger and heavier fuel cell stacks ultimately raise block fuel consumption (1,227.4 kg), diminishing overall efficiency.

For the 4-engine configuration (Fig. 6), the design benefits from a more favorable balance between propulsion integration, aerodynamic performance, and compliance with mission constraints. Key TLARs such as TOFL, climb time, and approach speed remain influential, but the required FCS power per nacelle drops to approximately 2.35 MW for the minimum block fuel solution, while the optimal wing area is reduced by roughly 10 m² compared to the 2-engine case. Overall, this configuration achieves the lowest installed power (9,419 kW) and lowest MTOM (44,864 kg) across all studies. Compared with the 2-engine option, this configuration also benefits from structural relaxation effects due to the distribution of propulsion system masses along the wing. The presence of four nacelles contributes to a measurable reduction in wing root bending moments, which helps reduce structural mass and improves the overall mass balance. The aerodynamic configuration is also favorable, with a clean drag coefficient-area product of 2.77 m². As a consequence, this solution exhibits the lowest block fuel consumption (1,181.6 kg for 1,000 nm and 328.1 kg for 250 nm).

The 6-engine configuration (Fig. 7) is basically driven by the same constraints as the 4-engine one but suffers from the growing aerodynamic penalties introduced by the increased number of nacelles. The overall installed power slightly increases to 9,937 kW for the optimal solution, while maintaining the same wing planform area of the optimal 4-engine option. The added nacelles and their interference effects result in the highest clean drag coefficient-area product among all configurations (2.87 m²), which significantly contributes to higher block fuel consumption (1,224.9 kg). Even though the 6-engine option achieves the highest OEI ceiling and offers the greatest redundancy, the penalty in cruise efficiency and complexity outweighs these benefits in the context of the current TLARs and design mission.

Fig. 5 Design mission block fuel contour plot for the 2-engine configuration study.

Fig. 6 Design mission block fuel contour plot for the 4-engine configuration study.

Fig. 7 Design mission block fuel contour plot for the 6-engine configuration study.

The main results of these optimization studies are summarized in Table 5, which compares the optimal wing areas, fuel cell powers, mass characteristics, aerodynamic properties, and performance metrics for each configuration. The results clearly highlight the 4-engine configuration as the most promising solution, offering the best compromise among mass efficiency, aerodynamic performance, propulsion integration, and regulatory compliance.

Table 5 Characteristics of optimal aircraft resulting from the parametric study on the number of engines.

	Number of engines		
	2	4	6
<i>Optimal aircraft design parameters</i>			
Wing planform area, m ²	109.83	100.0	100.0
Single FCS sizing power, kW	5,241	2,355	1,656
<i>Optimal aircraft characteristics</i>			
Sizing H ₂ mass, kg	1,624.6	1,564.1	1,622.1
Total installed power, kW	10,483	9,419	9,937
MTOM, kg	46,565	44,864	46,072
OEM, kg	35,508	33,861	35,017
Clean C _{D,0} × wing planform area, m ²	2.86	2.77	2.87
Block fuel 1,000 nm mission, kg	1,227.4	1,181.6	1,224.9
Block fuel 250 nm mission, kg	344.4	328.1	341.0

C. Current FAME concept aircraft

This section introduces the current reference aircraft configuration developed within the framework of the FAME project. The concept features a 4-engine layout, consistent with the findings of the parametric studies in Subsection V.B, and adopts an LH₂ tank venting pressure of 2.0 bar, as identified in Subsection V.A.

The current configuration is characterized by a wing planform area of 110 m² and an installed FCS power of 2.5 MW per nacelle, for a total installed power of 10 MW. Some assumptions used in defining this configuration are worth noting in comparison to those adopted in the parametric studies presented earlier in this manuscript. In particular:

- The maximum lift coefficients for take-off and landing are set to 2.52 and 2.82, respectively—slightly higher than the values of 2.35 and 2.65 used in previous sections. These more ambitious values reflect initial project-level targets, although only the detailed design and aerodynamic characterization of the high-lift system (to be carried out in WP2) will determine whether these values can be achieved in practice.
- The gravimetric index of the LH₂ tank is assumed to be 40%, slightly lower than the 41.1% value used in the optimal configuration of Subsection V.A. This more conservative assumption reflects the minimum performance threshold set for the FAME tank system.

At this stage, the current configuration does not yet include the drag contribution associated with the fuel cell cooling system, as its architecture and aerodynamic integration are still under development within WP2. This exclusion reinforces the rationale behind the slightly higher wing area and installed power margins embedded in the current design.

To assess the robustness of this reference configuration, the following subsection (Subsection V.D) investigates its resilience to degradations in key technology parameters—namely, fuel cell efficiency and additional drag due to the cooling system. This analysis provides insight into the flexibility of the current FAME concept in absorbing deviations from nominal subsystem performance while still meeting mission and regulatory constraints.

A 3D visual representation of the current FAME concept aircraft is provided in Fig. 8, while Table 6 offers key insights into its main characteristics and performance.

Fig. 8 Views of the current FAME aircraft concept.

Table 6 Main characteristics of the current FAME concept aircraft.

Parameter		Value
	<i>Geometry</i>	
Wing planform area		110 m ²
Wing aspect ratio		11.78
Fuselage length		37.53 m
	<i>Powerplant</i>	
Single FCS power		2,500 kW
Shaft power		2,093 kW
Propeller diameter		3.97 m
	<i>LH₂ tanks</i>	

Fwd tank internal volume	12.51 m ³
Aft tank internal volume	12.82 m ³
Split	49.4% / 50.6%
<i>Masses</i>	
Structural mass	12,688 kg
Powerplant mass	14,662 kg
Systems mass	3,593 kg
Furnishings	2,803 kg
Operating empty mass	35,157 kg
Maximum zero fuel mass	45,607 kg
Maximum take-off mass	46,245 kg
Maximum landing mass	46,245 kg
<i>Balance</i>	
Operative CG position (MAC %)	26.3%
Maximum forward CG position (MAC %)	14.0%
Maximum forward CG position (MAC %)	56.0%
<i>Aerodynamics</i>	
Clean (cruise) C _{D,0}	266 dc
Cruise maximum lift-to-drag ratio @operative CG	17.26
Take-off maximum trimmed lift coefficient @operative CG	2.52
Landing maximum trimmed lift coefficient @operative CG	2.82
<i>Performance</i>	
Take-off field length @MTOM, SL, ISA+15°C	1,247 m
Climb time to FL270 @MTOM, 210 KCAS, ISA	22.7 min
Maximum cruise Mach number @99.5% MTOM, FL270, ISA	0.625
300 ft/min maximum cruise Mach number @99.5% MTOM, FL270, ISA	0.594
Approach CAS @MLM	116.8 kn
Landing field length @MLM, ISA+15°C	1,263 m
Block fuel for 1,000 nm design mission, 101 passengers @95 kg, ISA	1,257 kg
Block time for 1,000 nm design mission, 101 passengers @95 kg, ISA	200.8 min
Block fuel for 250 nm typical mission, 101 passengers @95 kg, ISA	350 kg
Block time for 250 nm typical mission, 101 passengers @95 kg, ISA	63.6 min

D. Sensitivity analyses

This final study investigates the influence of key technological parameters—some of which are still subject to refinement at this stage—on both the design and the resilience of the current FAME concept aircraft. In particular, this sensitivity analysis focuses on two aspects:

- Deviations in fuel cell efficiency from the baseline value of 55% (at maximum power) used in previous analyses;
- The introduction of additional drag associated with the integration of a fuel cell cooling system, which has not yet been accounted for in the configurations discussed in earlier subsections.

The estimation of cooling drag follows a simplified, physics-based approach suitable for conceptual design studies. For each engine, the heat to be dissipated by the radiator is computed based on the FCS sizing power, the assumed fuel cell efficiency, and the fuel cell operating temperature, here taken as 120 °C. The external ambient conditions are set to ISA+15°C at sea level and a flight Mach number of 0.19, representative of the take-off segment, where thermal loads are expected to peak.

A radiator effectiveness of 70% is assumed. From this, the required mass flow rate of cooling air is determined, which enables estimation of the minimum inlet area. Once the inlet area is known, the associated drag penalty is estimated by calculating the momentum imbalance between inlet and outlet flows, assuming a given velocity recovery at the radiator exit. This additional drag is then expressed as a non-dimensional zero-lift drag coefficient increment, referenced to the wing planform area, and included as an additional term in the aircraft drag build-up, as suggested by Gudmundsson [31].

By exploring different combinations of fuel cell efficiency and cooling drag, this analysis serves two main objectives. First, it quantifies the direct impact of these parameters on key design drivers such as wing area and propulsion sizing. Second, it evaluates the robustness of the current FAME configuration against realistic degradations

in subsystem performance, identifying to what extent the aircraft can absorb such deviations without requiring a fundamental redesign.

Table 7 recaps the main findings from the parametric sensitivity analysis exploring the effect of fuel cell efficiency and cooling drag assumptions on the aircraft configuration and performance. Each table row corresponds to a fully optimized design solution that satisfies a specific set of technological assumptions and top-level requirements. Three distinct constraint sets are considered to progressively relax the most stringent performance requirements: (1) full compliance with all TLARs; (2) relaxation of the climb time to FL270; and (3) further relaxation of the cruise Mach number associated with 300 ft/min climb capability.

Across all cases, a clear trend emerges: reductions in fuel cell efficiency and reduced recovery of the cooling drag result in significantly heavier and less efficient aircraft. In the fully constrained configuration set, decreasing the fuel cell efficiency from 55% to 51%, while simultaneously reducing cooling drag recovery from 100% to 60%, leads to a block fuel increase of more than 110% on the 250 nm mission, with MTOM growing by over 17,000 kg and fuselage length increasing by over 5.6 meters. These degradations are driven by a combination of factors: the increased heat dissipation demand due to lower fuel cell efficiency, which translates into larger inlet areas and higher zero-lift drag; the resulting rise in required hydrogen mass; and the more powerful powerplant and larger wing dimensions needed to preserve mission capability.

When the time-to-climb requirement is relaxed (second block of the table), the optimization algorithm is able to slightly reduce the propulsion system size and limit the increase in wing area and fuel burn for the more penalizing configurations. This flexibility helps contain the block fuel penalties to some extent. For example, in the 51%/60% case, the relative increase in block fuel at 250 nm reduces from +111.2% (fully constrained) to +103.8%.

The greatest sensitivity relief occurs in the third scenario, where both time-to-climb and 300 ft/min cruise Mach number constraints are relaxed. Under these conditions, the optimization can better trade off cruise speed and climb capability to prioritize aerodynamic and fuel efficiency. As a result, the same penalizing 51%/60% configuration exhibits a smaller block fuel increase of +82.5% relative to the baseline. However, even in this relaxed scenario, performance losses remain substantial for the most degraded assumptions, underlining the critical role of fuel cell efficiency and drag management.

The differences between the most favorable scenario (55% fuel cell efficiency, 100% cooling drag recovery) and the most challenging one analyzed (51% efficiency, 60% cooling drag recovery) are further illustrated in Fig. 9. The former, already presented in Fig. 6, shows a broad feasible region, where the aircraft satisfies all TLARs with moderate design effort. Constraints such as TOFL, approach category, and time-to-climb are active, but do not significantly restrict the design space.

In contrast, Fig. 9 reveals the narrow and strained design landscape corresponding to the most demanding technological scenario. The combined effects of lower efficiency and higher cooling drag drive a substantial increase in the required wing area and fuel cell power to satisfy the TLARs. The feasible region becomes extremely limited, and constraints such as the 300 ft/min maximum cruise Mach requirement and the 25-minute time-to-climb limit begin to dominate the solution space. Notably, the take-off performance (TOFL constraint) becomes insensitive to further increases in fuel cell power, as the aircraft mass reaches levels where added power no longer compensates for the escalating inertia and drag. This saturation effect reflects the onset of a critical design regime, where traditional sizing levers lose effectiveness.

Table 7 Summary of optimal design and performance metrics for varying fuel cell efficiencies and cooling drag recovery assumptions.

Technological scenario		Optimal aircraft design parameters		Optimal aircraft characteristics			
Fuel cell efficiency	CL recovered drag	Wing area	FCS power	Sizing H ₂ mass	MTOM	Block fuel 250 nm mission	Δ Block fuel 250 nm mission ^a
%	%	m ²	kW	kg	kg	kg	%
<i>Constraint set 1: complete set of TLARs</i>							
55	100	100.00	2,355	1,564.1	44,864	328.1	0.0
	90	101.85	2,461	1,731.3	46,154	360.4	9.8
	80	102.75	2,682	1,932.7	48,219	400.8	22.2
	70	104.37	2,952	2,183.0	50,782	450.9	37.4
	60	107.30	3,318	2,518.3	54,253	518.0	57.9
53	100	100.38	2,500	1,656.3	46,286	349.2	6.4
	90	103.97	2,530	1,850.9	47,272	385.7	17.6
	80	105.38	2,789	2,095.3	49,760	434.7	32.5
	70	107.94	3,137	2,419.8	53,106	499.7	52.3
	60	112.44	3,617	2,873.8	57,768	590.9	80.1
51	100	103.27	2,500	1,755.0	46,956	369.9	12.7
	90	106.49	2,624	1,991.7	48,662	415.4	26.6
	80	108.58	2,933	2,295.2	51,714	476.3	45.2
	70	112.61	3,371	2,720.4	56,049	561.8	71.2
	60	119.66	4,037	3,371.3	62,685	693.1	111.2
<i>Constraint set 2: complete set of TLARs, time-to-climb to FL270 excluded</i>							
55	100	100.00	2,355	1,564.1	44,864	328.1	0.0
	90	105.67	2,220	1,714.3	44,766	351.5	7.1
	80	105.69	2,438	1,899.0	46,740	389.7	18.8
	70	106.26	2,713	2,128.6	49,223	437.1	33.2
	60	107.87	3,090	2,438.5	52,627	499.2	52.1
53	100	100.38	2,500	1,656.3	46,286	349.2	6.4
	90	107.81	2,286	1,835.3	45,852	378.1	15.2
	80	108.06	2,548	2,057.0	48,251	422.8	28.9
	70	109.28	2,888	2,349.1	51,392	481.9	46.9
	60	112.49	3,386	2,776.1	56,034	568.6	73.3
51	100	103.27	2,500	1,755.0	46,956	369.9	12.7
	90	110.23	2,362	1,969.5	47,081	404.1	23.2
	80	110.98	2,673	2,243.4	50,008	460.8	40.4
	70	113.25	3,101	2,624.7	54,076	538.8	64.2
	60	119.16	3,823	3,261.5	60,961	668.6	103.8
<i>Constraint set 3: complete set of TLARs, time-to-climb to FL270 and 300 ft/min maximum Mach number excluded</i>							
55	100	100.00	2,355	1,564.1	44,864	328.1	0.0
	90	105.67	2,220	1,714.3	44,766	351.5	7.1
	80	108.20	2,285	1,884.3	45,841	387.2	18.0
	70	110.66	2,349	2,050.1	46,900	421.9	28.6
	60	111.22	2,593	2,279.5	49,204	469.4	43.1
53	100	100.38	2,500	1,656.3	46,286	349.2	6.4
	90	108.01	2,274	1,834.6	45,782	377.8	15.1
	80	111.05	2,353	2,032.7	47,064	418.0	27.4
	70	113.60	2,459	2,240.3	48,539	461.4	40.6
	60	114.66	2,801	2,557.1	51,789	527.1	60.7
51	100	103.27	2,500	1,755.0	46,956	369.9	12.7
	90	110.69	2,336	1,968.5	46,932	404.0	23.1
	80	114.32	2,429	2,204.8	48,471	453.8	38.3
	70	116.89	2,615	2,471.8	50,659	509.3	55.2
	60	119.39	3,058	2,903.4	55,009	598.7	82.5

^a Values are referred to the best configuration at 55% fuel cell efficiency with 100% cooling drag recovery as baseline.

Fig. 9 Design mission block fuel contour plot for the 51% fuel cell efficiency, 60% CL drag recovery, fully constrained scenario.

Table 8 and Table 9 focus on the resilience analysis of an aircraft configuration with a wing planform area of 110 m² and an FCS power of 2.5 MW with respect to technology degradation. Table 8, in particular, reports the resulting trends in hydrogen sizing mass, MTOM, and block fuel consumption over a 250 nm mission. As expected, a decrease in fuel cell efficiency leads to increased waste heat, requiring larger radiator inlet areas and resulting in higher residual drag when the cooling drag recovery is incomplete. These effects cause a progressive increase in block fuel, with a more than 46% increase for the worst-case scenario (51% efficiency and 60% drag recovery) compared to the reference case (i.e., the current FAME concept of Subsection V.C). The associated increase in MTOM—from ~46.2 t to ~50 t—further compounds fuel consumption due to the snowball effect on energy requirements.

Table 9 complements this analysis by evaluating compliance with selected TLARs across the same scenarios. The degradation of both fuel cell efficiency and cooling recovery not only affects block fuel but also compromises aircraft performance. The take-off field length increases from 1,279 m to 1,511 m, approaching the 1400 m limit in several intermediate cases and exceeding it in the worst-case scenarios. More critically, time-to-climb to FL270 becomes increasingly problematic, growing from 22.4 minutes to over 90 minutes, clearly violating the 25-minute design constraint in all but the most favorable cases.

Maximum and 300 ft/min cruise Mach number performance are also sensitive to these variations. The reference configuration meets both thresholds comfortably (with values of 0.625 and 0.594, respectively), but both progressively deteriorate with decreasing efficiency and cooling recovery. In particular, the 300 ft/min Mach margin drops below the 0.55 target in scenarios below 53% efficiency and 70% CL drag recovery, signaling potential shortfalls in cruise performance and requiring either design modifications or a reassessment of the mission profile.

Overall, this analysis confirms that while the current FAME configuration offers a margin of robustness for moderate degradations in technology assumptions, its performance degrades nonlinearly under combined adverse conditions. Results underscore the importance of maintaining fuel cell efficiency at or above 53% and achieving at least 70–80% cooling drag recovery to avoid significant penalties in fuel consumption and TLARs compliance.

Table 8 Impact of fuel cell efficiency and cooling drag recovery on the inertia and fuel consumption characteristics of an aircraft with fixed wing planform area (110 m²) and single FCS sizing power (2.5 MW).

Technological scenario		Aircraft characteristics and fuel consumption			
Fuel cell efficiency	CL recovered drag	Sizing H ₂ mass	MTOM	Block fuel 250 nm mission	Δ Block fuel 250 nm mission ^a
%	%	kg	kg	kg	%
55	100	1,654.8	46,194	348.1	-0.5
	90	1,797.4	46,752	373.8	6.8
	80	1,945.7	47,337	400.1	14.3
	70	2,096.8	47,938	431.5	23.3
	60	2,235.1	48,479	460.2	31.5
53	100	1,727.8	46,693	363.3	3.8
	90	1,892.6	47,352	393.3	12.4
	80	2,060.5	48,015	422.4	20.7
	70	2,232.8	48,696	459.6	31.3
	60	2,359.6	49,192	485.1	38.6
51	100	1,809.2	47,261	380.4	8.7
	90	1,995.0	47,992	413.9	18.3
	80	2,187.3	48,758	449.6	28.4
	70	2,384.0	49,537	490.8	40.2
	60	2,499.8	49,995	513.2	46.6

^a Values are referred to the current FAME concept described in Subsection V.C.

Table 9 Impact of fuel cell efficiency and cooling drag recovery on the compliance with TLARs of an aircraft with fixed wing planform area (110 m²) and single FCS sizing power (2.5 MW).

Technological scenario		Aircraft key performance					
Fuel cell efficiency	CL recovered drag	TOFL @SL, ISA+15°C	Time-to-climb to FL270	Max. cruise Mach number	300 ft/min max. cruise Mach number	Approach CAS	LFL @SL, ISA+15°C
%	%	m	min	-	-	kn	m
55	100	1,279	22.36	0.625	0.594	120.4	1,324
	90	1,312	25.76	0.603	0.571	121.2	1,334
	80	1,347	30.50	0.582	0.550	121.9	1,340
	70	1,385	37.71	0.563	0.531	122.7	1,348
	60	1,420	50.63	0.546	0.513	123.4	1,355
53	100	1,312	22.85	0.624	0.592	121.1	1,334
	90	1,344	26.85	0.599	0.567	121.9	1,345
	80	1,386	32.55	0.577	0.544	122.8	1,352
	70	1,428	42.00	0.557	0.524	123.6	1,363
	60	1,462	62.20	0.539	0.505	124.3	1,366
51	100	1,334	23.47	0.621	0.590	121.8	1,353
	90	1,381	28.04	0.595	0.563	122.7	1,356
	80	1,428	35.07	0.571	0.538	123.7	1,365
	70	1,478	48.06	0.550	0.516	124.7	1,377
	60	1,511	91.15	0.532	0.496	125.3	1,382

VI. Conclusions

This study presented a comprehensive parametric design investigation of a liquid hydrogen fuel-cell-powered short-range aircraft within the Clean Aviation FAME project. A dedicated aircraft design framework was developed and applied to explore the design space under carefully selected performance requirements and technological constraints.

The analysis began with an optimization of LH₂ tank venting pressure, which revealed 2.0 bar as the most favorable trade-off between insulation and structural mass, yielding a compact and efficient design. A subsequent investigation of propulsion system architecture confirmed the superiority of a four-engine configuration with 2.35 MW per nacelle, providing the best balance of aerodynamic performance, mass distribution, and propulsion efficiency.

The current FAME aircraft concept, featuring 110 m² of wing planform area and 10 MW total installed power, was introduced and analyzed. A final sensitivity analysis explored the impact of fuel cell efficiency degradation and

cooling drag assumptions, demonstrating the concept's resilience under moderate technological deviations. However, results highlight the need to maintain fuel cell efficiency above 53% and cooling drag recovery above 70% to avoid performance shortfalls and ensure TLAR compliance.

Future activities at the conceptual design level within FAME WP2 will focus on further refining LH₂ tank integration, including the optimal selection of design parameters under varying technological assumptions for materials and insulation architectures. In addition, the sensitivity analysis framework will be expanded to assess the influence of other critical technology drivers, such as fuel cell gravimetric and volumetric efficiencies, as well as power line-specific weight, to provide a more complete evaluation of system-level trade-offs and integration constraints.

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